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**Identification of potential prognostic markers in Pancreatic Cancer using an integrated
approach of Gene expression profiling and network analysis**

Samvedna Singh, Shakti Sahi

School of Biotechnology, Gautam Buddha University, Greater Noida, India

Email: samvednasinghm@gmail.com

Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is one of the most aggressive types of cancer with a 5-year survival rate is Less than 20%. The present study aims to gain a better understanding of the mechanisms involved in the onset and progression of pancreatic cancer, as well as to identify reliable prognostic markers. We employed an integrated approach of gene expression profiling, screened for significantly differentially expressed genes coupled with epigenetic analysis. DNA methylation was characterised as changes such as hypomethylation and hypermethylation of multiple 5'-cytosine-phosphate-guanine-3' CpG island play a vital role in malignant cellular transformation by altering gene expression and cell differentiation. Therefore, it is considered a promising marker for early detection. Significance analysis of the gene expression and methylation profile was used to identify DEGs and DMRs between cancer tissues and normal tissues. Protein-Protein interaction networks were also built. Enrichment analysis and expression level verification of key driver genes were done which revealed their major role in the activation of proteoglycans pathway in cancer, cAMP signalling pathway, viral carcinogenesis, RAS oncogene pathway and, RAS signalling pathway. The key identified genes are also involved in the mechanism of RNA and nucleic acid binding invadopodia formation, and promoting cell adhesion in cancer cells, tumour growth, angiogenesis and invasion, negative regulation of translation, promoter hypermethylation etc which closely associates with pancreatic cancer development. Based on our results, we found potential and prospective clinical applications in IGF2BP3, IGF1 (Insulin-like growth family member), RAB31, RaC2, Rassf2 (member RAS oncogene family). BCAS1, VAV1, EGR2, cg20483763 (CABP4), cg20822628 (GATA5) have been identified to act as prognostic markers in the case of pancreatic cancer.

Keywords: Pancreatic cancer, Survival, Prognostic markers